

Political diplomacy and trade flows: analysing China's engagement in the Indo-Pacific

To what extent does China's political engagement influence its trade relationships with Indo-Pacific countries between 2000 and 2023?

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Abstract

This study examines the spillover effects of political engagement on trade engagement, focusing on China's relationships with 41 Indo-Pacific countries from 2000 to 2023. Using a novel dataset developed by Fathom Consulting that captures annual engagement scores across political and trade dimensions, the study applies a gravity model of trade to assess whether deeper diplomatic ties encourage stronger trade flows. Results from both a static and dynamic panel model indicate a consistent and statistically significant positive relationship between political and trade engagement, suggesting that China's diplomatic activity and soft power strategies contribute meaningfully to its trade integration in the region. To assess the role of formal agreements alongside political engagement, the analysis also includes the ASEAN-China Free Trade Area (ACFTA), which shows no clear effect on trade engagement. These findings offer new insights into the political drivers of trade and underscore the importance of sustained diplomatic engagement in shaping regional economic networks.

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1. Introduction

In recent years, the Indo-Pacific has emerged as a focal point of strategic rivalry between China and the United States, with the region often described as the arena where this competition is playing out (Heiduk and Wacker, 2020). As economic interdependence deepens and political alliances shift, understanding the relationship between diplomatic engagement and trade flows has become crucial. China's expanding influence in the region, facilitated not only through its economic size and trade agreements but also through political diplomacy and soft power, raises questions about the nature and implications of its international engagement strategies. This thesis examines how China's political engagement with Indo-Pacific countries affects its trade relationships.

At the time of writing, the United States has announced a wave of new tariffs on Chinese imports, with the potential for broader trade measures, prompting renewed fears that a new phase of US-China trade tensions may be unfolding. This has reignited concerns about the use of trade policy as a geopolitical tool. These developments underscore the importance of exploring the role of engagement in fostering stable trade relations.

This thesis is motivated by two primary gaps in existing literature. First, while many studies examine how political disputes affect trade, few consider the trade-creating effects of sustained and positive diplomatic engagement. Second, analyses focusing on China often rely on narrow or event-based measures of political relations, notably the Political Relations Index developed by Tsinghua University, which is based on Chinese media sources and may reflect one-sided interpretations of international events. These approaches often overlook the broader and more sustained dimensions that form political engagement.

To address this, this thesis uses a novel dataset from Fathom Consulting, an economic consultancy, which provides annualised engagement scores for China's interactions with 41 Indo-Pacific countries between 2000 and 2023. These scores span five dimensions: trade, political, military, cultural, and financial, though this thesis focuses on political and trade engagement only. Rather than focusing on discrete political events, the dataset captures a broader pattern of sustained diplomatic interaction, including variables such as high-level diplomatic visits, alignment in United Nations voting, and China's provision of development aid.

To examine the relationship between political and trade engagement, this thesis applies a gravity model of trade using panel data. The gravity model predicts bilateral trade flows based on the size of trading partners' economies and the distance between them. This approach is adapted from the model used by HM Treasury to assess the effects of Brexit. This model is tailored in this thesis to incorporate political engagement scores, trade agreements, and control variables specific to the Indo-Pacific context. Alongside a static specification, a dynamic model is estimated using the two-step System Generalised Method of Moments estimator. This accounts for the persistence of trade flows over time and addresses concerns around endogeneity. This thesis contributes new empirical insights into the role of political engagement in shaping international trade flows. It offers a perspective on China's foreign policy strategy in one of the most strategically and economically important areas of the world. Specifically, it makes three contributions to the existing literature: first, it introduces a novel political engagement variable quantifying China's diplomatic and soft-power interactions with Indo-Pacific countries; second, it examines the role of a key trade agreement in the Indo-Pacific region and its effect on trade outcomes; and third, it incorporates dynamic modelling to assess how trade relationships evolve over time, capturing adjustment processes often overlooked in static frameworks.

The remainder of this thesis is structured as follows: Section 2 outlines the background; Section 3 reviews the literature; Section 4 describes the data; Section 5 sets out the methodology; Section 6 presents results and robustness checks; Section 7 discusses findings and policy implications; and Section 8 concludes.

2. Background

The term "Indo-Pacific" refers to a geopolitical concept that has gained prominence over the past two decades, gradually replacing the earlier "Asia-Pacific" in global discourse (Heiduk and Wacker, 2020). This shift reflects a broader recognition of the interconnectedness of the Indian and Pacific Oceans and their surrounding regions as a single strategic area. The term gained significant momentum during Donald Trump's first presidential term when the United States introduced its "Free and Open Indo-Pacific" strategy, which aimed to promote a rules-based international order while countering China's expanding influence. Since then, the Indo-Pacific has become central to the foreign and security policies of nations such as Japan, Australia, India, France, and several Southeast Asian states (Heiduk and Wacker, 2020). China, however, views the Indo-Pacific concept as a U.S.-led containment strategy and

avoids using the term in its official narratives (Heiduk and Wacker, 2020). Today, the Indo-Pacific serves as the principal arena for the intensifying strategic rivalry between the United States and China, underscoring its geopolitical and geo-economic significance.

The strategic importance of the Indo-Pacific lies in its geography and its pivotal role in the global economy. Central to this is the South China Sea, which connects Southeast Asia with the Western Pacific and serves as a critical maritime corridor, often described as the "throat" of global sea routes (Kaplan, 2011). This region includes key chokepoints, such as the Straits of Malacca, Sunda, Lombok, and Makassar, through which around one-third of global shipping passes (UNCTAD, 2016). Control over these routes provides substantial influence over global trade and energy supplies. The South China Sea is also resource-rich, with an estimated 190 trillion cubic feet of natural gas and 11 billion barrels of proved and probable oil reserves (Asia Maritime Transparency Initiative, 2023). The Indo-Pacific region accounts for over half of the global population and more than one-third of global GDP (World Bank, 2025a; World Bank, 2025b). These demographic, economic, and geographic factors combine to make the region central to international competition and cooperation. A full list of countries included in the Indo-Pacific, along with a regional map, is provided in Appendix Figure 1A.

Over the past few decades, China has emerged as a global superpower, transforming from a relatively closed economy into a dominant force in international trade and politics. It is currently the world's second-largest economy by nominal GDP and the largest by purchasing power parity (PPP) since 2016 (IMF, 2024). This significant economic rise has significantly shaped the strategic dynamics of the Indo-Pacific region, where China has steadily expanded both its political and economic influence.

A key driver of China's global influence has been its rapid expansion in trade. Since joining the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 2001, China's integration into the global trading system has accelerated dramatically. China's WTO accession reduced trade barriers and signalled their alignment with international standards, boosting investor confidence and global demand for Chinese exports (Lin and Wang, 2008). As shown in Figure 1, Chinese exports have almost quadrupled in current USD terms since the early 2000s, with imports following a similar upward trend. China's position within global supply chains, as a manufacturing hub and a major consumer market, has reinforced its importance in regional trade flows.

Figure 1: China's trade in goods and services

This economic transformation has occurred alongside growing regional political engagement. China has taken an increasingly active role in multilateral platforms such as the ASEAN-China Free Trade Area, the Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation forum, and more recently, the Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (Feng, 2022). Participation in these forums has allowed China to deepen diplomatic relationships and position itself as a crucial player in regional cooperation and development. In many cases, these political ties have preceded economic collaboration, including trade agreements, and infrastructure projects.

One such infrastructure initiative is the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), launched in 2013 as a cornerstone of China's foreign policy. The BRI seeks to enhance connectivity and cooperation across Eurasia, Africa, and Oceania through infrastructure development, trade facilitation, financial integration, policy coordination, and cultural exchange (Li, 2020). Economically, it aims to address domestic overcapacity by redirecting surplus industrial and financial resources abroad. Strategically, the BRI is widely regarded as a geostrategic manoeuvre to expand China's regional influence, secure critical trade routes, and leverage economic tools to deepen political and security ties with neighbouring and partner countries (Li, 2020). It is also seen as a response to perceived challenges posed by U.S.-led initiatives such as the Trans-Pacific Partnership and the Free and Open Indo-Pacific strategy. However, the BRI has faced significant geopolitical opposition, particularly from countries such as India, Japan, and the United States, which view it as a mechanism for advancing Chinese hegemony (Li, 2020).

This thesis examines China’s engagement in the Indo-Pacific region. It adopts Evan Resnick’s (2001) definition of engagement as the “comprehensive establishment and enhancement of contacts with states across multiple issue areas” (p. 559). While engagement encompasses various dimensions, this study focuses on political engagement and trade engagement. China’s political engagement in this context refers to the use of soft power strategies such as cultural diplomacy and development aid, while trade engagement can be defined here as the bilateral exchange of goods and services (exports and imports) between China and Indo-Pacific nations. This focus aims to highlight the spillover effects of political initiatives on economic relationships in the region.

To investigate this relationship, this study explores the extent to which China’s political engagement in the Indo-Pacific has generated spillover effects on trade engagement. By examining variation across countries and over time, the study aims to assess whether stronger political ties with China are associated with increased trade flows. Figure 2 shows that both political and trade engagement between China and the Indo-Pacific have been steadily increasing since 2000, highlighting a trend that warrants closer examination. Understanding this relationship contributes to broader debates on how rising powers leverage diplomatic channels to reshape trade networks, particularly in a strategically significant region such as the Indo-Pacific.

Figure 2: Average trade and political engagement between China and the Indo-Pacific, 2000–2023

3. Literature review

3.1 Political relations and trade

The relationship between political relations and international trade has been widely debated in literature for several decades. Early theoretical frameworks addressing this intersection of politics and trade have largely been shaped by realist and liberalist perspectives. Realists argue that states prioritise security and are more likely to trade with allies than with adversaries, with trade patterns reflecting broader strategic alignments. This logic suggests that political relations are a key determinant of trade flows, often captured by the phrase “trade follows the flag” (Pollins, 1989). In contrast, liberalism holds that economic interdependence promotes cooperation, as the mutual benefits of trade outweigh the incentives for conflict. Gartzke (2001) argues that interdependence not only raises the costs of war but also facilitates credible signalling through market-based interactions, thus states can communicate their intentions and reduce uncertainty in international relations.

In response to the growing complexity of global trade networks, many scholars question whether traditional theories still adequately capture the relationship between politics and trade. One prominent contribution that challenged the traditional expectations was Davis and Meunier’s (2011) *“Business as Usual? Economic Responses to Political Tensions”*. Davis and Meunier argue that traditional frameworks no longer adequately capture the nature of political-economic linkages in the globalised era. Using a gravity model of bilateral exports and imports, and event data from Reuters (via the King-Lowe dataset), they found little evidence that political disagreements, defined as hostile rhetoric, public demonstrations, or diplomatic strain, translated into a measurable drop in trade flows. They argue that high sunk costs make political retaliation via trade costly and thus less likely.

However, the “business as usual” thesis has faced significant empirical challenge in recent years. A follow-up case study by Li and Liu (2017), focused specifically on China and Japan in the wake of the 2012 Diaoyu/Senkaku Islands dispute, found that Japanese exports to China in highly salient and visible goods, such as cameras, fell significantly after the incident. This suggests that public sentiment during periods of political tension can override economic interests, and that trade may no longer proceed unaffected when political sensitivities are high. In contrast, Chinese exports to Japan remained stable, pointing to potential asymmetries in economic retaliation.

A growing body of literature has focused on China, examining how political relations and shocks influence its trade with key partners. Many of these studies rely on the Political Relations Index (PRI) developed by Tsinghua University, which assigns monthly scores to China's bilateral relationships on a scale from -9 to +9, based on significant political or diplomatic events. Du et al. (2017), for example, construct a trade-filtered version of the PRI and use a monthly Vector Autoregression (VAR) model to analyse short-term dynamics between China and some of its major trading partners. They find that political shocks do affect trade with China, but these effects tend to be short-lived, typically fading within a few months.

Whitten et al. (2020) also use the PRI in their analysis of China's trade with twelve major trading partners. Employing a VAR and a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), they investigate both short- and long-run dynamics, finding that political shocks can have persistent effects on trade, although the magnitude and duration of these effects vary by country. Cointegration tests confirm the existence of a stable long-run relationship, underscoring the sustained relationship between political and trade ties. To address concerns about endogeneity, Whitten et al. argue that the PRI is unlikely to be influenced by trade itself, as the events used to generate the index are almost exclusively political or military in nature. Similar conclusions are reached by Xia et al. (2025), who use firm-level trade data and a gravity model to show that improved political relations significantly boost trade between China and BRI countries.

This thesis argues that the use of the PRI dataset developed by Tsinghua University introduces a potential source of bias. The index is constructed by researchers evaluating major political events based on reports from People's Daily and China's Ministry of Foreign Affairs, meaning it reflects China's perspective on its bilateral relationships. The interpretation and severity of events may differ if assessed by the counterpart country or by a neutral third party. This raises important concerns around objectivity and the risk of measurement error in capturing the true state of political relations.

Several case-specific studies further reinforce the economic consequences of political disputes involving China. For instance, Fuchs and Klann (2013) use a gravity model to test whether visits from the Dalai Lama correlate with lower Chinese imports. The results suggest a significant negative effect during the Hu Jintao presidency, where diplomatic rebukes translated into real economic consequences. Wang (2015) shows that Sino-Philippine trade volume declined significantly after periods of territorial disputes over the South China Sea, particularly in cases of more severe disputes.

A paper that links well to this thesis is Rose (2019), which examines how soft power influences trade outcomes, a concept often associated with China's approach to expanding global influence (Nye, 2004). Rose finds that countries whose leadership is viewed favourably abroad tend to export more. Using Gallup World Poll data and a gravity model, the study estimates that declining approval of U.S. leadership during the Obama–Trump transition reduced U.S. exports by at least 3 billion dollars. This suggests a broader understanding of political relations, where public perception, not just formal diplomacy or disputes, can meaningfully influence trade flows. However, Rose's reliance on survey data introduces limitations, as such measures capture sentiment rather than actual behaviour. People may express approval or disapproval without this necessarily translating into concrete actions. In contrast, this thesis uses a dataset based on observed political actions, offering a more objective measure of political engagement, based on observable behaviour rather than public opinion.

Overall, the literature increasingly supports the view that deteriorating political relations tend to reduce trade, even if the extent and persistence of this effect vary across studies. Case specific evidence, as well as broader empirical work using the Tsinghua PRI, consistently shows that political tensions, whether in the form of territorial disputes, diplomatic frictions, or public disapproval, can disrupt bilateral trade flows. However, there is still limited understanding of how ongoing, relationship-building forms of political engagement shape trade outcomes. Most studies focus on episodes of conflict or downturns in relations, rather than considering political engagement as a continuous and multidimensional process. Furthermore, much of the literature relies on China's own interpretation of events and is restricted to a narrow group of trading partners. No existing study takes a regional perspective on the Indo Pacific, despite its growing strategic and economic importance. This thesis addresses these gaps by using a novel, third-party dataset to analyse how China engages politically across the Indo Pacific, and whether these patterns of engagement influence trade outcomes beyond periods of geopolitical crisis.

3.2 Theoretical framework: the gravity model

This thesis employs the gravity model of trade. This model, first introduced by Jan Tinbergen in 1962, provides a framework for estimating bilateral trade flows by drawing on Newton's theory of gravitation. It states that bilateral trade between two countries is proportional to their respective sizes measured by their GDP, and inversely

proportional to the geographic distance between them. Thus, the bilateral trade between two countries is given by:

$$Trade_{A,B} \propto \frac{(GDP_A)^\alpha (GDP_B)^\beta}{(Distance_{AB})^\zeta} \quad (1)$$

Where $\alpha, \beta, \zeta \approx 1$ (Chaney, 2011).

Anderson and van Wincoop (2003) argue that while widely used, many previous empirical applications of the gravity equation lack a solid theoretical foundation. They highlight that traditional models often omit multilateral resistance, the idea that trade between two regions depends not just on their bilateral barriers, but also on how those barriers compare to each region's average trade barriers with other partners. This omission leads to biased estimates and limits the model's capacity to assess how changes in trade policy, such as tariff reductions, would affect trade flows. Anderson and van Wincoop (2003) address these limitations by developing a theoretically consistent gravity equation that incorporates multilateral resistance terms, allowing for more accurate estimation and meaningful policy analysis, this can be seen in Equation (2):

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(X_{ijt}) = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln(Y_i) + \beta_2 \ln(Y_j) + (1 - \sigma)\rho \ln(d_{ij}) + (1 - \sigma)\ln(b_{ij}) \\ & - (1 - \sigma)\ln(P_i) - (1 - \sigma)\ln(P_j) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where $\ln(X_{ijt})$ is the log of exports from region i to j , explained by GDP in each region (Y_i), bilateral distance (d_{ij}), and a border dummy (b_{ij}) which equals 1 if region i and j are in the same country. σ denotes the elasticity of substitution between goods. P_i and P_j are multilateral resistance terms, reflecting how trade barriers with all other partners influence bilateral trade.

This thesis employs a model similar to that of the Treasury's gravity model, which was used to predict the impact of Brexit (Gudgin et al., 2017). The specification employed by the Treasury can be seen in Equation (3):

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(X_{ijt}) = & \beta_0 + \gamma_t + \beta_1 \ln(Y_{it} Y_{jt}) + \beta_2 \ln(POP_{it} POP_{jt}) + \beta_3 EU2_{ijt} \\ & + \beta_4 EU1_{ijt} + \beta_5 EEA_{ijt} + \beta_6 FTA_{ijt} + \varepsilon_{ijt} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The model includes GDP and population variables multiplied across trading partners to reflect bilateral economic size. γ_t denotes year dummies for $t = 1 \dots T$. α_{ij} is the country-pair fixed effect. Four additional dummies capture trade arrangements: $EU2_{ijt}$ equals 1 if both countries are in the euro area, $EU1_{ijt}$ if only one is, EEA_{ijt} if the origin is in the European Free Trade Area, and FTA_{ijt} if the origin has a free trade agreement with the EU. These are used by the Treasury to estimate the effects of different trade agreements, including EU membership.

An important feature of this gravity equation is the inclusion of pairwise country and time fixed effects (Gudgin et al., 2017). The country-pair fixed effects, α_{ij} account for all time-invariant factors influencing bilateral trade flows, such as geographical distance or historical ties. As these fixed effects absorb such influences, there is no need to include distance or explicit multilateral resistance terms in the model. Head and Mayer (2014) emphasise that estimating gravity models with country fixed effects effectively captures multilateral resistance, ensuring consistency with the theoretical foundations of the model.

The Treasury's gravity model analysis showed that trade flows would decline if the UK exited the EU, regardless of the alternative trade arrangements considered. The results indicated that reduced integration with the EU would lead to lower bilateral trade volumes, ultimately diminishing the UK's economic openness (HM Treasury, 2016). These findings demonstrate the gravity model's effectiveness in capturing how changes in trade arrangements affect long-term trade flows.

3.3 The ASEAN–China Free Trade Area

This thesis utilises the ASEAN-China Free Trade Area (known here on as ACFTA) as a trade agreement dummy, reflecting its potential role in shaping trade engagement between China and ASEAN member states.

A key question in the literature is whether ACFTA brings mutual economic opportunity or increases competition between the countries involved. On the one hand, the removal of tariffs and non-tariff barriers is expected to stimulate intra-regional trade by lowering transaction costs and encouraging market integration. On the other hand, given the structural similarities in production and demand across China and ASEAN countries, some scholars have suggested that the agreement could intensify export competition within the region.

Hastiadi (2011) examines the effects of regional integration in East Asia, covering China, Korea, Japan and ASEAN, using a Two Stage Least Squares approach and a fixed effects model. Hastiadi (2011) argues that in the short-term, competitive pressures in export markets arising from overlapping comparative advantages and production structures exist. However, he finds in the long run, regional integration is expected to support and encourage export growth across the entire East Asian region.

Sheng et al. (2014) extend the traditional gravity model by incorporating trade in parts and components to assess the impact of ACFTA on ASEAN–China trade. Focusing on trade in intermediate goods, rather than solely on final goods, is particularly relevant in the East Asian context, where production often depends on components being sourced from multiple countries, particularly in industries such as semiconductors and machinery. Their findings suggest that ACFTA has had a significantly greater effect on trade than previously estimated using standard gravity models. This outcome is partly attributed to the region’s increasingly integrated supply chains and the growing importance of component trade used in manufacturing.

Similarly, Yang (2014) also uses a gravity model with disaggregated data, and find a significant and positive relationship between ACFTA and export growth. These effects are observed across both agricultural and manufactured goods, with particularly strong results in sectors such as chemical products, machinery and transport equipment.

Several studies have focused specifically on the impact of ACFTA on Indonesia. Darmanto et al. (2021) identify trade creation effects in coffee, rubber and palm oil, but also note trade diversion in the cocoa sector. Ibrahim et al. (2010), using a Global Trade Analysis Project model, find that while Indonesia’s trade with other ACFTA members may fall due to the entry of Chinese imports into ASEAN markets, exports to China are expected to increase as a result of the agreement. Their model estimated a 50.5 percent increase in China’s exports to ASEAN following the agreement.

Darma (2017) finds that ACFTA results in trade creation across all member countries and encourages trade with external partners under agreements such as the ASEAN–Korea Free Trade Area and the ASEAN–India Free Trade Area, without clear evidence of trade diversion. This suggests that ACFTA may not only strengthen internal regional trade but also support wider engagement with the regional economy.

In summary, the literature generally finds that ACFTA has had a positive impact on trade flows within the region, though effects vary across sectors and countries. While

short-term competition may arise in overlapping export markets, most studies find evidence of trade creation and deeper regional integration in the long run. These findings support the inclusion of ACFTA as a trade agreement dummy in this thesis's gravity model analysis.

4. Data

4.1 Data overview

This study uses annual data from 41 Indo-Pacific countries spanning the years 2000–2023.

The primary dataset used is Fathom Consulting's "Engagement Scores", which offer a structured measure of China's interactions with other countries across five dimensions: trade, political, financial, cultural, and military. As far as this thesis is aware, no other publicly available dataset captures China's political relations with comparable breadth. The most commonly used alternative in similar studies, the Tsinghua University events dataset, relies on media reports from Chinese sources, raising concerns about bias and selective framing. Moreover, the Tsinghua dataset focuses on recorded political events, whereas this thesis takes a broader view of China's sustained political relationships. As such, Fathom Consulting's scores are better suited to the research objective.

While engagement scores were constructed across five categories, this thesis focuses exclusively on trade and political engagement, which are most relevant to assessing the spillover effects of political activity on trade outcomes.

The trade engagement scores are based on variables drawn from nine strategically significant sectors, including high-technology exports, telecommunications, new energy, and industrial manufacturing. These sectors were identified as strategically important to both China and the Indo-Pacific region. The variables were sourced from a range of databases, with full source details provided in Table A1 in the Appendix. To ensure classification consistency, over 1,000 export product categories were coded using the North American Industry Classification System. Products spanning multiple sectors were classified under each relevant category. The trade engagement scores capture China's dual role as both a supplier and a purchaser of key exports of Indo-Pacific countries.

The political engagement scores were constructed to measure the extent of diplomatic and political interaction between China and Indo-Pacific countries. These include high-level diplomatic exchanges, alignment in UN voting patterns and signals of China's policy stance, such as trade agreements or other state-led interventions (liberalising or restrictive). Data was collected from a combination of existing datasets and manual searches, as many variables lacked a single comprehensive source. A complete list of variables, sources, units, and time coverage is available in the Appendix in Table A2. A summary of the trade and political engagement variables is shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1. List of variables in trade engagement and political engagement scores

Trade engagement variables	Political engagement variables
Trade measures on China	ODA % GDP
Trade measure by China	ODA % total
Agricultural goods export to China % GDP	OOF % GDP
Agricultural goods export to China % total	Approved destination status
Agricultural goods import from China % GDP	Visa free travel
Agricultural goods import from China % total	Trade agreements
Manufactured consumer textiles export to China % GDP	High-level diplomatic visits to China
Manufactured consumer textiles export to China % total	High-level diplomatic visits from China
Manufactured consumer textiles import from China % GDP	Sponsorship of region football teams
Manufactured consumer textiles import from China % total	Diplomatic representation % population
Minerals, Chemicals, metals and non-metals export to China %	Size of China embassy, m2
Minerals, Chemicals, metals and non-metals export to China %	UN votes (all)
Minerals, Chemicals, metals and non-metals import from China	China installed telecoms infrastructure
Minerals, Chemicals, metals and non-metals import from China	China media/AI surveillance training
High-tech products including IT export to China % GDP	COVID-19 vaccine donations total % population
High-tech products including IT export to China % total	Recognition of Taiwan
High-tech products including IT import from China % GDP	Inter-country relations
High-tech products including IT import from China % total	FPI
Other machinery and equipment export to China % GDP	
Other machinery and equipment export to China % total	
Other machinery and equipment import from China % GDP	
Other machinery and equipment import from China % total	
Old energy exports to China % GDP	
Old energy exports to China % total	
Old energy imports from China % GDP	
Old energy imports from China % total	
New energy exports to China % GDP	
New energy exports to China % total	
New energy imports from China % GDP	
New energy imports from China % total	
Not otherwise categorised exports to China % GDP	
Not otherwise categorised exports to China % total	
Not otherwise categorised imports from China % GDP	
Not otherwise categorised imports from China % total	

Source: Fathom Consulting

4.2 Data processing and normalisation

The dataset forms an unbalanced panel due to missing observations across countries and years. To manage this, different techniques were applied depending on the nature of each variable. These included averaging across available years, assigning zeros where the value was reasonably inferred to be zero, extending point-in-time data across the series where appropriate, or leaving values missing where data gaps were

genuine. A summary of the transformations applied to each variable is provided in Tables A1 and A2 in the Appendix.

After the data collection, variables were normalised using z-scores¹ to facilitate comparability across countries and over time. First, category-level engagement scores, such as those for political engagement, were calculated by taking the mean of the z-scores of all variables within that category, ensuring that each variable contributed equally to the final measure. Within each category, the weight was distributed equally among the included variables. Since trade engagement, for example, comprised a greater number of variables than political engagement, individual trade-related variables contributed a smaller proportion to the overall engagement score, whereas political engagement variables had a relatively higher weight.

To mitigate the impact of missing data, a redistribution approach was implemented, in which the weight of a missing variable was reallocated proportionally among the remaining variables within the same engagement category. This adjustment ensured that missing observations did not disproportionately affect the engagement scores.

The final engagement scores were scaled between 0 and 10 to improve comparability across time. The lowest observed score across all countries and years was assigned 0, and the highest was assigned 10.

4.3 Sample selection and control variables

The initial country list included all Indo-Pacific states except North Korea, which was excluded due to persistent data limitations. To ensure sufficient data availability, a threshold was applied: countries missing 15% or more of variables across all five engagement categories were excluded. As a result, several U.S. overseas territories (American Samoa, Guam, Northern Mariana Islands) and one French overseas collectivity (Wallis and Futuna) were omitted.

Additional control variables used in the analysis include population and GDP. Population data comes from the IMF's World Economic Outlook Database. GDP

¹ A z-score standardises a variable by indicating how many standard deviations a given value is from the mean of its distribution. This allows variables with different units or scales to be compared on a consistent basis.

figures are taken primarily from the World Bank, however, where data was unavailable, IMF forecast data is used. All GDP values are expressed in current US dollars.

Finally, the model includes a time-variant dummy variable for the ACFTA. The agreement came into effect in January 2010 for Brunei, Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore, and Thailand, and in 2015 for Cambodia, Laos, Myanmar, and Vietnam. The dummy equals 1 for countries and years in which the agreement was active, and 0 otherwise.

Table 2 reports summary statistics for the main variables used in the analysis. Most variables have means close to their median values, suggesting minimal skew in the data. The observed variation across trade flows, political engagement, and standard gravity controls supports their inclusion and reflects differences across countries and over time.

Table 2. Summary statistics

Variable	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.
<i>Ln(Trade engagement)</i>	0.1407	0.1711	0.7307	-0.3866	0.2726
<i>Ln(Political engagement)</i>	0.4156	0.4694	1.5140	-3.0770	0.4543
<i>Ln(Partner country GDP)</i>	23.0623	23.0604	29.4672	16.4521	3.2934
<i>Ln(Partner country population)</i>	29.4158	29.7138	30.5148	27.8227	0.8995
<i>Ln(China GDP)</i>	14.5858	14.8247	21.0751	7.4983	3.1766
<i>Ln(China population)</i>	21.0257	21.0284	21.0776	20.9540	0.0409

5. Methodology

This section outlines the economic rationale and model specifications of the gravity model employed in this analysis.

5.1 Econometric considerations

All variables except the trade agreement dummy have been log-linearised. This allows us to model relations in terms of percentages, making the coefficient estimates interpretable as elasticities, and thus the results more intuitive. It also narrows the range of variables with large values, particularly population and GDP (Wooldridge, 2020 p187).

Zeros in the raw data were addressed using techniques outlined in Section 4.2, with additional detail in Table A1 and A2 in the Appendix. In the final index, there is only one instance of a zero value: Taiwan in 2022. This observation was deemed an outlier likely due to COVID-19. An impulse dummy was applied to capture this observation without distorting the index.

An important consideration for this study is the country-specific effects that do not vary over time but may influence both political and trade engagement. To account for this, a panel data methodology is employed, which allows for the control of individual heterogeneity across countries.

Two main estimation techniques are commonly used in panel data analysis, depending on the assumptions about the unobserved effects (Gómez-Herrera, 2012). The fixed effects (FE) estimator allows for arbitrary correlation between the time-invariant unobserved effects and the regressors, making it a robust choice when such correlation is likely. In contrast, the random effects (RE) estimator relies on the orthogonality assumption, that the unobserved individual effects are uncorrelated with the explanatory variables. Under this assumption, RE offers more efficient estimation by exploiting both within- and between-entity variation through Generalised Least Squares (Wooldridge, 2020 p470).

The Hausman test evaluates this assumption, allowing us to determine which model is more appropriate. Under the null hypothesis of no correlation between the unobserved effects and the regressors, the RE estimator is both consistent and efficient. A Hausman test conducted in this study yielded a p-value of 0.6018, meaning the null could not be rejected. This suggests that the RE estimator is appropriate for this dataset. Consequently, RE was chosen as the main static model for this analysis. This aligns with previous gravity model studies that use RE when orthogonality holds (Oh and Selmier, 2008, Kavallari et al., 2008 and Fratianni and Oh, 2007).

In addition to addressing potential correlation between regressors and unobserved heterogeneity, FE estimation also provides a way to account for multilateral resistance terms (MRTs), which are important in gravity model applications. MRTs capture the influence of a country's overall trade openness or remoteness from global markets, beyond bilateral relationships (Anderson and van Wincoop, 2003). Although these effects are not directly quantified in this study, the FE model helps to absorb them through time-invariant country-pair controls. While the decision to use RE over FE presents a potential limitation in this respect, the focus of this study is not on modelling

the structure of global trade frictions, but instead examines directional trade flows and their relationship with political engagement. The inclusion of FE estimations as a robustness check strengthens confidence in the results and mitigates concerns about any bias arising from unobserved multilateral influences.

In all static specifications, standard errors are clustered at the country level to address potential heteroskedasticity and serial correlation.

Endogeneity poses a potential problem to any model due to the violation of the exogeneity assumption, an assumption which is crucial for the estimation of unbiased results. Endogeneity arises when the explanatory variables are correlated with the error term, making those regressors endogenous and hence their estimated partial effects will suffer from bias. RE estimation mitigates endogeneity to an extent, as it removes the time invariant unobserved effects. However, it does not fully resolve the issue.

In gravity models, endogeneity can also arise due to the persistence of trade flows, meaning that countries tend to trade with the same countries they have in the past. For countries that traded extensively in the past, businesses have set up distribution and service networks in the partner country, which has led to entrance and exit barriers due to sunk costs. Consumers may have developed a preference for products from the partner country due to habit formation. It is therefore very likely that current bilateral trade levels between those countries are high. This was confirmed by Eichengreen and Irwin (1997) who added lagged trade as a regressor to their gravity model and showed that lagged trade is indeed important. However, the introduction of dynamics into panel data models renders the FE estimator biased and inconsistent, because the lagged endogenous variable correlates with the error term (Nickell, 1981).

Therefore, this study also estimates a dynamic gravity model using a Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) approach. The GMM model includes lagged dependent variables while avoiding the endogeneity problem by instrumenting endogenous variables. Martinez-Zarzoso et al. (2009) supported the use of dynamic gravity models in the context of trade agreements, demonstrating their effectiveness when both static and dynamic models were estimated.

This study applies the two-step system GMM estimator, as proposed by Arellano and Bover (1995) and Blundell and Bond (1998), which improves efficiency by incorporating additional moment conditions. To account for unobserved country-

specific effects, the model uses the forward orthogonal deviations transformation. This method restructures the data by subtracting the average of all future available observations from each current observation, rather than using past values as in first differencing. This approach therefore maintains orthogonality between transformed errors and lagged regressors, while also preserving more observations. Hayakawa (2009) finds that GMM models using forward orthogonal deviations generally perform better than those using first differences, thus further validating this methodological choice.

5.2 Specification:

5.2.1 Static model

As discussed in Section 3, this study will utilise a model similar to that of the Treasury's gravity model. This is restated in the equation below:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(X_{ijt}) = & \beta_0 + \gamma_t + \beta_1 \ln(Y_{it}Y_{jt}) + \beta_2 \ln(POP_{it}POP_{jt}) + \beta_3 EU2_{ijt} \\ & + \beta_4 EU1_{ijt} + \beta_5 EEA_{ijt} + \beta_6 FTA_{ijt} + \varepsilon_{ijt} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

While this gravity model includes the logged product of bilateral variables such as GDP and population (i.e. $\ln(Y_{it}Y_{jt})$ and $\ln(POP_{it}POP_{jt})$) this study separates these into individual logged terms (i.e. $\beta_1 \ln(POL_{ijt})$, $\beta_2 \ln(Y_{it})$, $\beta_3 \ln(Y_{jt})$, $\beta_4 \ln(POP_{it})$, and $\beta_5 \ln(POP_{jt})$). Separating the terms allows the model to estimate distinct effects for each term. This distinction is especially valuable in the Indo-Pacific context, where countries vary greatly in economic size and demographic weight, for example, the influence of China's GDP or population is unlikely to be equal to that of smaller regional economies such as Fiji. A similar approach is taken by the CEPII Gravity Database, which uses unilateral variables to allow researchers to specify gravity equations with greater flexibility and clarity in interpretation (Conte et al., 2022).

This leaves the static model in this study with the following specification:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(X_{ijt}) = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln(POL_{ijt}) + \beta_2 \ln(Y_{it}) + \beta_3 \ln(Y_{jt}) + \beta_4 \ln(POP_{it}) + \beta_5 \ln(POP_{jt}) \\ & + \beta_6 ACFTA_{it} + \lambda_j + \varepsilon_{ijt} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Where t denotes time (year), i denotes China, j denotes the Indo-Pacific partner country.

Variables:

X_{ijt} : Trade engagement between China (i) and Indo-Pacific country j in year t

POL_{ijt} : Political engagement between China (i) and Indo-Pacific country j in year t

Y_{it}, Y_{jt} : GDP of countries China and Indo-Pacific country j in year t

POP_{it}, POP_{jt} : Population of countries China and Indo-Pacific country j in year t

$ACFTA_{it}$: Dummy variable equal to 1 if the ASEAN-China Free Trade Agreement is in effect for country j in year t , and 0 otherwise

λ_j : Country-fixed effects for Indo-Pacific country j (since i is always China)

ε_{ijt} : Time-varying error term

5.2.2 Dynamic model:

A dynamic panel model is estimated using the GMM, alongside the static specification. The GMM model includes the same explanatory variables as the static model, with the addition of a lagged dependent variable, $\text{Ln}(X_{ijt-1})$, to account for persistence in trade engagement over time, as seen in Equation (6).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Ln}(X_{ijt}) = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Ln}(X_{ijt-1}) + \beta_2 \text{Ln}(POL_{ijt}) + \beta_3 \text{Ln}(Y_{it}) + \beta_4 \text{Ln}(Y_{jt}) \\ & + \beta_5 \text{Ln}(POP_{it}) + \beta_6 \text{Ln}(POP_{jt}) + \beta_7 ACFTA_{it} + \lambda_j + \varepsilon_{ijt} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

This structure aligns with a partial adjustment model, which captures the idea that countries have a desired level of trade engagement but adjust toward it gradually rather than instantaneously. The theoretical model consists of two components: a static equation defining the desired level of trade engagement, and a dynamic adjustment process:

$$y_t^* = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 x_t + u_t \quad (7)$$

$$y_t - y_{t-1} = \lambda(y_t^* - y_{t-1}) \quad (8)$$

Where y_t^* is the desired level of trade. Substituting Equation (7) into Equation (8) yields the estimating equation:

$$y_t = \lambda \alpha_0 + (1 - \lambda)y_{t-1} + \lambda \alpha_1 x_t + \lambda u_t \quad (9)$$

This can be estimated using a general ARDL model:

$$y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 y_{t-1} + \beta_2 x_t + \beta_3 x_{t-1} + v_t \quad (10)$$

Under the partial adjustment assumption, the restriction $\beta_3 = 0$ applies. The speed of adjustment, λ , can be derived from the estimated coefficient on the lagged dependent variable:

$$\beta_1 = (1 - \lambda) \Rightarrow \lambda = (1 - \beta_1)$$

This framework allows the dynamic model to capture both the persistence in trade flows and the gradual adjustment toward a long-run equilibrium level of trade engagement.

5.2.3 Expected signs

This study expects political engagement to have a positive relationship with trade engagement. Political engagement constitutes diplomatic visits, development aid, and soft power initiatives that help foster trust and cooperation between countries. Stronger political ties may reduce uncertainty and improve communication and perceptions, encouraging firms and governments to increase bilateral trade. In the Indo-Pacific region, where there are competing strategic interests, these relationships may be particularly important in shaping trade flows.

The ACFTA is also expected to support trade engagement by reducing tariffs and other non-tariff barriers between China and member countries. Trade agreements are typically associated with increased market access, thus encouraging firms to increase their cross-border activity.

While GDP and population are included as control variables, it is expected that they will have a positive relationship with trade engagement. Larger economies and more populous countries tend to trade more due to greater production capacity, consumer base, and market size. Controlling for GDP and population helps to isolate the effect of political engagement from underlying structural differences in country size and development.

In the dynamic specification, the lagged trade engagement is expected to have a positive coefficient. As discussed in Section 5.1, this reflects the idea that trade flows are persistent over time, with previous levels of engagement influencing future trade relationships.

6. Results

This study employs both static and dynamic models to estimate the effects of political engagement and trade agreements on trade engagement. The analysis also considers the impact of the ACFTA. This section presents the key findings, while the subsequent discussion section contextualises them within the existing literature.

6.1 Static model

Table 3 reports the results of the static model, estimated using Pooled Ordinary Least Squares (POLS), fixed effects, and random effects specifications. The results indicate that political engagement has a positive and statistically significant effect on trade engagement, this is seen across all specifications. A poolability test (p -value < 0.001) rejects the null hypothesis, supporting the need for a model that accounts for unobserved heterogeneity. A subsequent Hausman test yields a p -value of 0.6018, which is insufficient to reject the null hypothesis that the random effects estimator is consistent and efficient. Therefore, the RE model is deemed the most appropriate specification for this analysis, and the following analysis focuses primarily on the results of this model.

Table 3. Static model results

Variable	Pooled OLS (1)	FE (2)	RE (3)	RE with interactions (4)
Intercept	-26.0990 (0.5696)	-	-23.1880 (0.4304)	-20.1992 (0.4904)
<i>Ln(Political engagement)</i>	0.2619*** (0.0000)	0.2774*** (0.0000)	0.2723*** (0.0000)	0.2775*** (0.0000)
<i>Ln(Partner country GDP)</i>	0.0897*** (0.0000)	-0.0152 (0.7045)	0.0170 (0.7502)	-0.0204 (0.7052)
<i>Ln(Partner country population)</i>	0.0141 (0.1982)	0.0506 (0.9180)	0.0797* (0.0929)	0.0790 (0.1001)
<i>Ln(China GDP)</i>	0.1919* (0.0714)	0.2563*** (0.0008)	0.2354*** (0.0009)	0.2417*** (0.0007)
<i>Ln(China population)</i>	0.08750 (0.7072)	0.6620 (0.6910)	0.7096 (0.6286)	0.5555 (0.7034)
<i>ACFTA</i>	-	-0.0078 (0.9232)	-0.0157 (0.8397)	3.5535*** (0.0003)
<i>Ln(Partner country GDP) × ACFTA</i>	-	-	-	-0.1315*** (0.0003)
<i>Ln(Political engagement) × ACFTA</i>	-	-	-	-0.3157* (0.0548)
R^2	0.4936	0.6423	0.6348	0.6462
n	984	984	984	984

Note: Figures in brackets are clustered standard errors. A dummy variable for Taiwan in 2022 is included to control for an extreme outlier in political engagement. This anomaly is likely attributable to the lingering effects of COVID-19 disruptions

*** ≤ 0.01 , ** ≤ 0.05 , * ≤ 0.1

The random effects model (column 3) demonstrates a strong fit, with an R^2 of 0.6348, indicating that 63% of the variation in trade engagement is explained by the model's explanatory variables. Among the statistically significant variables, both $\ln(\text{Political engagement})$ and $\ln(\text{China GDP})$ are positively signed and statistically significant at the 1% level. These results are in line with expectations: greater political engagement fosters increased trade engagement while a larger Chinese economy enhances trade flows through increased import demand, export capacity, and deeper integration into regional supply chains. The coefficient on $\ln(\text{Partner country population})$ is positive and marginally significant at the 10% level, however, this falls below the 5% significance threshold adopted for this study. The coefficients on $\ln(\text{Partner country GDP})$, $\ln(\text{China population})$ and $ACFTA$ are all statistically insignificant.

When interaction terms are introduced to the RE model (column 4), the explanatory power of the model improves slightly, with the R^2 increasing to 0.6462. The coefficient on $ACFTA$ becomes positive and highly significant ($p < 0.001$), suggesting that membership in $ACFTA$ boosts trade engagement. The interaction between $\ln(\text{Partner country GDP})$ and $ACFTA$ is negative and significant ($p < 0.001$), potentially indicating that larger economies derive relatively smaller marginal gains from the agreement. This may reflect the fact that larger economies tend to have more diversified trade networks, and therefore may be less reliant on trade with China. The interaction term between $\ln(\text{Political engagement})$ and $ACFTA$ is negative and statistically significant at the 10% level, however this falls below this study's 5% threshold.

6.2 Robustness checks using a dynamic model

To assess the robustness of the static model findings, a dynamic panel data model was estimated using the Generalised Method of Moments. This approach addresses potential endogeneity and serial correlation by including a lagged dependent variable.

Table 4. Correlation matrix

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. $\ln(\text{Trade engagement})$		0.2966	0.1482	-0.0619	0.3446	0.3561	0.2864
2. $\ln(\text{Political engagement})$	0.2966		-0.2091	-0.1167	0.2161	0.2338	0.1573
3. $\ln(\text{Partner country GDP})$	0.1482	-0.2091		0.3900	0.0917	0.0932	0.0092
4. $\ln(\text{Partner country population})$	-0.0619	-0.1167	0.3900		0.0226	0.0230	0.0226
5. $\ln(\text{China GDP})$	0.3446	0.2161	0.0917	0.0226		0.9749	0.3117
6. $\ln(\text{China population})$	0.3561	0.2338	0.0932	0.0230	0.9749		0.3146
7. $ACFTA$	0.2864	0.1573	0.0092	0.0226	0.3117	0.3146	

Prior to estimation, a correlation matrix (Table 4) revealed strong multicollinearity between $\ln(\text{China GDP})$ and $\ln(\text{China population})$. Given that $\ln(\text{China population})$ was statistically insignificant in all static specifications, it was excluded from the dynamic model as a further test of robustness and to reduce multicollinearity, thereby improving the reliability of the estimates.

To avoid potential distortions introduced by the economic shocks of the COVID-19 pandemic, observations from 2020 to 2023 were excluded. The dynamic model is therefore estimated using data from 2000 to 2019, ensuring that results reflect typical trade dynamics unaffected by the pandemic period.

Table 5. Dynamic model results

Variable	Baseline model (1)	Dummy included (2)	Dummy with interaction terms (3)
$\ln(\text{Trade engagement})(-1)$	0.5917*** (0.0000)	0.5945*** (0.0000)	0.5924*** (0.0000)
$\ln(\text{Political engagement})$	0.1111*** (0.0000)	0.1039*** (0.0000)	0.0992*** (0.0005)
$\ln(\text{Partner country GDP})$	-0.0010 (0.5989)	-0.0083 (0.6993)	-0.0334 (0.3920)
$\ln(\text{Partner country population})$	0.1364*** (0.0000)	0.1731* (0.0711)	0.2443 (0.1915)
$\ln(\text{China GDP})$	0.0920*** (0.0000)	0.0919*** (0.0000)	0.0998*** (0.0000)
<i>ACFTA</i>	-	-0.0270 (0.2753)	-0.0581* (0.0592)
$\ln(\text{Partner country GDP}) \times \text{ACFTA}$	-	-	-0.0007 (0.7071)
$\ln(\text{Political engagement}) \times \text{ACFTA}$	-	-	-0.0432 (0.5937)
<i>Prob(J-statistic)</i>	0.3543	0.3355	0.3320
<i>n</i>	902	902	902

Note: *** ≤ 0.01 , ** ≤ 0.05 , * ≤ 0.1

The J-test, introduced by Hansen (1982), assesses the validity of overidentifying restrictions by testing whether the instruments are jointly exogenous, a key consideration in dynamic GMM models where the number of instruments exceeds the number of endogenous variables. In this analysis, the dynamic GMM model employs lagged variables as instruments. The J-statistic for the model that includes the ACFTA

dummy (column 2, Table 5) yields a p-value of 0.3355, indicating that the null hypothesis of instrument validity cannot be rejected. This supports the reliability of the instruments used in the specification.

The estimated coefficients of the dynamic model, as seen in Table 5, largely align with theoretical expectations. As anticipated, $\ln(\text{Trade engagement})_{(-1)}$ is positively associated with current trade engagement ($p < 0.001$), reinforcing the persistence of trade relationships over time. The coefficient on $\ln(\text{Political engagement})$ remains positive and statistically significant at the 1% level across all model specifications, reinforcing the conclusion that greater political engagement is associated with increased trade engagement. As with the static model, $\ln(\text{China GDP})$ remains positive and significant at the 1% level, suggesting that China's economic size continues to play a significant role in shaping trade flows in the region. The magnitude of $\ln(\text{Political engagement})$ and $\ln(\text{China GDP})$ are smaller than in the static model. This is expected, as the inclusion of the lagged dependent variable in the dynamic specification accounts for part of the variation in trade engagement, reducing the size of other coefficients.

In the dynamic specification that includes the trade agreement dummy and interaction terms (column 4), the coefficient on *ACFTA* becomes negative and only weakly significant at the 10% level, falling below the 5% benchmark adopted in this study. This contrasts with the static model, where *ACFTA* was positively signed and highly significant. Similarly, the interaction term $\text{ACFTA} \times \ln(\text{Partner country GDP})$ which was significant in the static specification, is no longer statistically significant in the dynamic model.

To further explore the dynamics of trade engagement, a partial adjustment model was estimated using the dynamic GMM specification. Based on the coefficient on the lagged dependant variable ($\beta_1 = 0.5945$), the speed of adjustment can be calculated at $\lambda = 1 - \beta_1 = 0.4055$. This implies that approximately 40.6% of the gap between actual and desired trade engagement is closed each year. The result indicates that while trade relationships do respond to changes in political and economic conditions, the adjustment process is gradual rather than immediate.

7. Discussion

While all model specifications yielded broadly similar results in terms of coefficient signs and significance, this discussion focuses on the dynamic GMM model. This

approach mitigates concerns around endogeneity and accounts for the persistence of trade flows over time, offering a more robust interpretation of the relationship between political and trade engagement. The consistency of results across specifications suggests robustness to explanatory variables, COVID-19, and dynamic effects.

This thesis has taken a novel approach to examining how political relations influence trade by using a broader definition of political engagement, capturing both diplomatic and soft-power interactions, and an original dataset not yet explored in existing literature. It provides a fresh perspective on how political factors shape bilateral trade. Additionally, it considers the role of regional trade agreements, specifically ACFTA, in influencing trade patterns within the Indo-Pacific. These findings contribute to the literature on political determinants of trade by offering empirical evidence of a spillover effect from political to trade engagement. By isolating China's political engagement as a predictor, the analysis highlights diplomacy and soft power as tools for fostering economic ties, which is especially relevant in the Indo-Pacific, where China's influence continues to grow.

The coefficient on political engagement is consistently positive across specifications, with a value of 0.10 in the dynamic model that includes the ACFTA dummy. This implies that a 1% increase in political engagement is associated with a 0.1% increase in trade engagement. This result supports existing literature that identifies a positive link between political relations and trade flows (Whitten et al., 2020; Xia et al., 2025; Fuchs and Klann, 2013), and aligns with Rose's (2019) findings on the role of public sentiment in shaping trade outcomes. Although modest in magnitude, the effect is likely to accumulate over time, particularly given the observed persistence in trade flows.

The dynamic GMM estimation shows strong evidence of persistence in trade engagement over time, with the coefficient on the lagged dependent variable consistently around 0.59. This implies that a 1% increase in trade engagement in the previous year is associated with a 0.59% increase in the current year, reinforcing the importance of historical relationships in trade.

China's GDP also has a positive coefficient (0.09 to 0.10), suggesting that as China's economy grows, its capacity to engage in trade, as both a producer and consumer, increases, supporting expectations.

The ACFTA dummy is negative in the dynamic model, both in the specification with the dummy alone and with interaction terms (Table 5, columns 2 and 3). However, in both cases, the coefficient falls short of the 5% significance threshold adopted in this study. This contrasts with prior studies such as Sheng et al. (2014), Yang (2014), and Darma (2017), which find that the agreement had trade-creating effects. One possible explanation for the absence of a significant effect lies in how the variable is measured. In this thesis, the dummy takes the value of 1 only after full implementation, potentially missing earlier phases of liberalisation as countries begin adjusting policies before formal enforcement. Additionally, it is possible that the influence of ACFTA is already captured through the broader political engagement variable, which reflects cooperation across multiple domains, including trade policy.

These findings offer important implications for policymakers. They suggest that political engagement can be an effective tool for fostering trade, especially in the Indo-Pacific context where formal trade agreements may not always yield strong results. Amid renewed trade tensions, exemplified by the recent wave of US tariffs, these findings emphasise the need for stable political relationships to support resilient trade networks.

In summary, the results address the central research question of this thesis, showing that political engagement has a measurable and consistent influence on trade, while the effect of formal trade agreements appears more limited. These findings highlight the growing importance of diplomatic and soft-power strategies in shaping economic relations across the Indo-Pacific.

8. Conclusion

This study set out to examine the extent to which China's political engagement influences its trade engagement with Indo-Pacific countries. By using a novel dataset of political and trade engagement scores developed by Fathom Consulting, the study adopted a new approach to measuring political relationships, moving beyond event-based data to focus on sustained diplomatic and policy-based interactions. Furthermore, it also assessed the impact of a China-inclusive trade agreement (ACFTA) on trade engagement with members.

The results of the dynamic gravity model provide strong evidence of persistence in trade engagement, as shown by the positive and significant coefficient on the lagged dependent variable. Political engagement was consistently associated with higher levels of trade engagement, indicating that sustained diplomatic relationships and soft

power initiatives can support the development of trade ties. China's GDP was positively associated with trade engagement as expected, reinforcing the role of economic size in shaping trade flows. In contrast, ACFTA membership did not show a robust relationship with trade engagement, indicating that formal trade agreements alone may be insufficient to drive stronger economic integration in the absence of broader political alignment.

The results offer several important implications for policymakers in both China and the Indo-Pacific region. First, the finding that political engagement has a consistent and positive relationship with trade engagement highlights the strategic value of diplomacy and soft power as tools for economic statecraft. For China, this reinforces the importance of maintaining active political relationships, not only through formal agreements but also through high-level diplomatic visits, cultural exchanges, and development assistance, as a way to sustain and deepen trade ties. For governments within the Indo-Pacific region, the findings suggest that fostering stronger diplomatic channels with China may bring tangible trade benefits, particularly in the absence of formal trade agreements.

Second, the limited impact of ACFTA membership, along with the non-significant interaction terms, suggests that formal trade agreements alone may not be sufficient to generate significant gains in trade engagement. This could imply that the quality of political relationships may matter more in practice.

While the findings offer new insight into the political determinants of trade, this study is not without limitations. The engagement scores rely on a constructed framework that may include subjective judgement, for example in the variable selection and weighting. Additionally, the ACFTA dummy variable may not fully capture the phased nature of trade liberalisation, as countries often begin adjusting policies and reducing tariffs prior to the official implementation date. In this study, the dummy was activated only once the agreement was fully in effect, but greater consideration could be given to how and when such trade agreements start to influence trade behaviour.

Future research could build on this work by incorporating additional dimensions of engagement included in the dataset, such as financial, military, or cultural engagement, which were excluded from this study due to scope constraints. This could offer a more holistic view of how different types of country-level engagement influence trade patterns. Another potential extension would be to examine intra-regional engagement among Indo-Pacific countries themselves. While this study has focused

on China's relationships with the region, intra-regional engagement may also play a meaningful role in shaping trade and political dynamics. In an era of great power rivalry, regional interactions are sometimes overlooked, yet they may have important implications for how countries engage politically and in trade. Understanding these dynamics could also help capture third-party effects, where a country's trade is not only influenced by its bilateral political engagement with China, but also by broader patterns of interaction among countries in the Indo-Pacific region.

Overall, this study contributes to the extensive literature on the relationship between political relations and trade by providing new empirical evidence from the Indo-Pacific region. It highlights the importance of political ties in shaping trade outcomes and offers a framework for understanding how China, through its distinct use of diplomacy and soft power, seeks to expand and sustain its trade relationships. In doing so, it sheds light on how political engagement can be used not only to build influence, but also to strengthen economic integration in a geopolitically significant region.

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Appendix

Figure 1A: Map of Indo-Pacific region.

Note: Countries included in this study are: Australia, Bangladesh, Bhutan, Brunei, Cambodia, China, Fiji, French Polynesia, Hong Kong, India, Indonesia, Japan, Kiribati, Laos, Macau, Malaysia, Maldives, Marshall Islands, Micronesia, Mongolia, Myanmar, Nepal, New Zealand, Palau, Papua New Guinea, Philippines, Samoa, Singapore, Solomon Islands, South Korea, Sri Lanka, Taiwan, Thailand, Timor-Leste, Tonga, Tuvalu, Vanuatu, Vietnam, Cook Islands, Nauru, New Caledonia, and Niue.

Table A1. Trade engagement variables – sources, transformations, and missing data protocols

Variable name	Variable source	Source coverage	Transformation(s)	Missing value protocol
Exports to and imports from hub 'Agricultural goods'	Base pour l'Analyse du Commerce International (BACI)	2000 - 2022	% GDP, % total	If missing set to zero; use latest available value for 2023
Exports to and imports from hub 'Manufactured consumer textiles'	Base pour l'Analyse du Commerce International (BACI)	2000 - 2022	% GDP, % total	If missing set to zero; use latest available value for 2023
Exports to and imports from hub 'Media, entertainment and culture'	Base pour l'Analyse du Commerce International (BACI)	2000 - 2022	% GDP, % total	If missing set to zero; use latest available value for 2023
Exports to and imports from hub 'Military goods'	Base pour l'Analyse du Commerce International (BACI)	2000 - 2022	% GDP, % total	If missing set to zero; use latest available value for 2023
Exports to and imports from hub 'Minerals, chemicals and metals'	Base pour l'Analyse du Commerce International (BACI)	2000 - 2022	% GDP, % total	If missing set to zero; use latest available value for 2023
Exports to and imports from hub 'New energy'	Base pour l'Analyse du Commerce International (BACI)	2000 - 2022	% GDP, % total	If missing set to zero; use latest available value for 2023

Exports to and imports from hub 'Old energy'	Base pour l'Analyse du Commerce International (BACI)	2000 - 2022	% GDP, % total	If missing set to zero; use latest available value for 2023
Exports to and imports from hub 'Other machinery and equipment'	Base pour l'Analyse du Commerce International (BACI)	2000 - 2022	% GDP, % total	If missing set to zero; use latest available value for 2023
Exports to and imports from hub 'Other high-tech products'	Base pour l'Analyse du Commerce International (BACI)	2000 - 2022	% GDP, % total	If missing set to zero; use latest available value for 2023
Exports to and imports from hub 'Not elsewhere categorised'	Base pour l'Analyse du Commerce International (BACI)	2000 - 2022	% GDP, % total	If missing set to zero; use latest available value for 2023
Net liberalizing state interventions by and on hub (over trade in goods and services, foreign investment and labor force migration)	Global Trade Alert	2008 - 2023	Number of liberalizing minus anti-competitive measures in force	Use average of 2008 - 2010 for years 2000 - 2007; if missing set to zero

Source: Fathom Consulting

Table A2. Political engagement variables – sources, transformations, and missing data protocols

Variable name	Variable source	Source coverage	Transformation(s)	Missing value protocol
High-level diplomatic visits to and from China	CEIAS, Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the P.R.C., U.S. Department of State, Wikipedia	2000 - 2023	Number of visits each year	Set to zero
Official development assistance from China	AidData	2000 - 2021	% GDP, % total	If country in dataset but value missing, set to zero; if country not in dataset, leave blank
Other official flows from China	AidData	2000 - 2021	% GDP	If country in dataset but value missing, set to zero; if country not in dataset, leave blank
China sponsorship of country soccer team	Football Kit Archive	2000 - 2023	1 = sponsor is from China, 0 = otherwise	NA
Diplomatic representation (presence of China embassy and/or consulates)	USEmbassy.gov, Wikipedia, Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the P.R.C, various other sources	2000 - 2023	2 = embassy, 1 = consulate (or embassy, no consulate), 0 = no embassy or consulate in country, score as % population	NA
Size of China embassy, m2	USEmbassy.gov, Wikipedia, Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the P.R.C, various other sources	2024	m2	NA
Votes with China in UN (all votes)	Voeten et al (2009) 'United Nations General Assembly Voting Data'	2000 - 2022	% total votes where China disagreeS	Leave blank
Chinese installed telecoms infrastructure	Shahbaz, A. (2018) 'The Rise of Digital Authoritarianism'	2018	1 = telecom infrastructure installed by China, 0 = otherwise	Leave blank
Chinese media training	Shahbaz, A. (2018) 'The Rise of Digital Authoritarianism'	2018	1 = Participation in seminars hosted by China, 0 = otherwise	Leave blank
COVID-19 vaccine donations total	Duke Global Health Innovation Center, U.S. Department of State	2020 - 2023	% population	Set to zero

Relationship with China on a 'peace-rivalry' spectrum	Delfi et al (2021) 'Peace Data: Concept, measurement, patterns and research agenda'	2000 - 2020	1 = serious rivalry, -0.5 = rivalry, 0 = no relationship, 0.5 = negative peace, 1 = warm cooperation	Leave blank
Visa-free travel to China	Department of Homeland Security, Ministry of Foreign Affairs China, and Wikipedia	2000 - 2023	1 = visa-free entry, 0 = need visa	NA
Country has 'Approved destination status' from China	Arlt et al (2012) 'How China's Approved Destination Status Policy Spurs and Hinders', various other sources	2000 - 2023	1 = on approved destination status list, 0 = not on list	NA
Trade agreements with China	U.S. Department of State, Nedeljk, Christoph (2023) 'Countries of the Belt and Road Initiative'	2000 - 2023	1 = any trade agreements exist, 0 = none	NA
Distance to China's Fathom Political Indicator (FPI) score	Fathom Political Indicator	2000 - 2022	1 = closer to China., 0 = otherwise	Leave blank

Source: Fathom Consulting